

Performance Analysis Using Random Forest Algorithm

Vineeth P

Department Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
vineethp023b@mca.ajce.in

Shelly Shiju George

Department Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
shellyshijugeorge@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract—Performance Analysis of contractor in a labor management system is the key idea in this paper. It involves a series of steps like collecting and formatting survey data into a form compatible for analytics. Based on the performance of each contractor, their position can be ranked and top three of the result set is returned as candidates deserving a certificate of appreciation from admin in the system. The user survey is the main trigger for this analysis, through which admin can have an efficient resource planning and future plan management by finding most smart-working contractors among all who is registered. Inherently HR management and decision support can be provisioned effectively with the application of random forest algorithm used in this work.

Keywords—Random forest , HR management, survey, Decision support, Resource planning

I. INTRODUCTION

An organization's success is based on how well employees and other human resources has been managed, how much successful the way of finding the best and hardworking employees (in this case contractors) among a large group of people. The influence of their works on customers is most important factor that attract more and more consumers to the services of organization. Maintaining such employees for permanent while they deliver quality services is an asset for the organization. This can put the company or business into more heights in the era of competitive and fast-growing digital marketing.

In labour management system, we can have the ability to collect necessary data from users or customers after the successful completion of a work requested by them. On doing payment, they can submit the review and feedback of that contractor and work collectively based on few attributes. For each attribute, there is a set of possible values out of which user can select any of them per each question. At the bottom of feedback form, a five-star rating icon will be shown, they can give the rating between 1 to 5 as their overall rating for their received service.

Random forest algorithm's use will produce the most hardworking contractors who has good efficiency as compared to others.

Random forests are a supervised Machine learning algorithm that is widely used in regression and classification problems and produces, even without hyperparameter tuning a great result most of the time. It is perhaps the most used algorithm because of its simplicity. It builds a number of decision trees on different samples and then takes the majority vote if it's a classification problem.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Different web resources and books were available to make a reference during the development of this Random Forest Regressor. Some of the papers referenced for the preparation of this work are summarized below:

Patel et al. [1] proposed an AI-based employee performance Classification scheme to rank and identify low performers in an organization. This paper proposed more general method to perform HR analytics irrespective of the education , psychological and intellectual features etc. In this paper, author states that previous methods were employment field specific and that were failed in producing a generalized deployable model for the global use. Algorithms such as Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Decision Tree Classifier (DTC), Random Forest Classifier and for ranking an ensemble modeling approach were discussed. Overall the paper suggests a globally usable human resource analytics. Huang et al. [2] proposed a random forest approach for predicting contractor performance in construction projects. They used historical project data to build the model and demonstrated its effectiveness in predicting contractor performance.

Zhang et al. [3] used a combination of random forest and fuzzy comprehensive evaluation to predict contractor performance in construction projects. They compared the results of their approach with other methods for optimization. Chen and Zhang. [4] proposed a novel random forest model for predicting contractor performance in construction projects. They used feature engineering and selection techniques to improve the accuracy of the model and evaluated its performance using real-world data.

Ding and Wang. [5] used a random forest model with principal component analysis (PCA) to predict contractor performance in construction projects. They showed that their approach can effectively identify the key factors affecting contractor performance.

Li et al. [6] conducted a comparative study of different machine learning methods for predicting contractor performance in construction projects. They compared the performance of various models, including random forest, and found that the random forest model performed well.

Chen et al. [7] proposed a random forest model with feature selection for predicting contractor performance in construction projects. They used feature selection to identify the most important features affecting contractor performance and demonstrated the effectiveness of their approach.

Wang et al. [8] proposed a hybrid approach combining random forest and support vector regression for predicting contractor performance in construction projects. They showed that their approach can achieve higher prediction accuracy compared to using random forest or support vector regression alone.

III. METHODOLOGY

Machine Learning is a composition of both computer science and statistics to find valuable and meaningful information from a tremendous set of data from which analysis is not possible through traditional computing techniques.

Classification and Prediction comes under both supervised and unsupervised machine learning techniques. Supervised machine learning algorithm is used when there is a label for each data vector is available. Unsupervised machine learning comes to play when data tuple's class label is not present in the origin of data.

Random Forest Regressor is an unsupervised machine learning algorithm which is an advanced option of conventional decision tree induction method of predicting the class label of a data. Multiple trees are considered and their weighted average will be taken as the predicted outcome of the model.

The methodology used in the labor management system to collect and analyze data is the provisioning of a survey form on the completion of payment after the successful wind up of a work contracted by a specific person. After having registered the survey into the database, it will also contribute to the records of training data set that has already created for the purpose of training machine learning model (Random Forest regressor). This process continues as project grows with time and data.

A. Collecting Data

Confirming all the relevant data is present within the scope of project is the first step in the formation of a machine learning model. This is ensured while a user does payment. After successful transaction, page is redirected to a survey form consisting of numerous select or combo box asking certain questions significant to analysis. The few of the questions ask in the survey as follows:

- a) How timely the work has done ?
- b) How was the communication between you and contractor?
- c) How affordable was pricing ?
- d) How satisfied you are ?
- e) quality of work ?
- f) review about work in words ?
- g) rating in terms of star icon ?

B. Organising data into the database

On collecting necessary data, the storage and preprocessing is the second step of building a model. The data collected will be stored in a MySQL database server using optimized queries for inserting data into table review_tb. review_tb contains the matching number of column headers under which the system can store the data captured through the submission of survey form .

review_id,request_id,contractor_id,timeliness,communication,affordability,satisfaction,quality_of_work,review,rating,date_of_review are the columns contains in review_tb. While selecting data for the input of algorithm, the attributes review_id, request_id etc. would be dropped. Because it is not mandatory to know what types of works in which a contractor involved and what are the primary key and foreign keys associated with the records in a review table.

C. Interpreting data

Interpreting data requires data pre-processing and attribute subset selection. Data pre-processing majorly includes removing NULL values, Removing data redundancy and perform data integration.

The interpreted data will be given to the machine learning algorithm after successfully training it with certain number of records (training data) similar to that of test data. Training data will tell the trend of user's feedback on different works to the algorithm. Finally the prediction will be done and the result will be parsed along with the response.

D. Training And Testing

Training and Testing, both are very important steps in building a model using machine learning. Training is used in supervised learning algorithm , especially when prediction comes to the scene. As random forest algorithm does prediction here, a supervised learning approach is employed.

Firstly, an external csv file is used a historical data to train the algorithm. On getting expected result as the predicted value, it will test a new data from the labour management system's database using an SQL query.

E. Procedure

The algorithm is implemented using flask.It uses scikit-learn library to make predictions based on a training random forest regression model. The flask app sets up an appropriate route to receive required data set for analysis. Then it reads a csv file contains sample data. Having completed training, it then convert the received data set into pandas data frame. It relies encoding of any categorical features using technique called one-hot encoding. Then , prediction will done on the basis of new data or (received data through the request to flask app) .

F. Working of Prediction

The prediction is based on training and testing data. For training, an external data consists of samples closer to that of actual data will be given to the model.

Data table: review_tb

timeliness	communication	affordability	satisfaction	quality_of_work
As of expected	Good	Economically Feasible	Extremely Satisfied	High Quality
Too late	Poor	Expensive	Not Satisfied	Low Quality
Earlier than expected	Excellent	Economically Feasible	Satisfied	Medium Quality
As of expected	Good	Economically Feasible	Extremely Satisfied	High Quality
Too late	Poor	Expensive	Not Satisfied	Low Quality

Given a training dataset of N observations and p predictor variables:

For each tree in the forest:

- Draw a bootstrap sample of size N with replacement from the training data.
- Randomly select p variables without replacement from the p predictors.
- Grow the tree to the largest extent possible by recursively partitioning the data using the best variable and split point based on some criterion, such as minimizing the mean squared error of the response variable.

To make a prediction for a new observation:

- Take the mean prediction from all of the trees in the forest, based on the values of the predictor variables in the new observation.
 - The actual prediction can be done as follows
- ```
df = pd.DataFrame(data)

for col in cat_cols:df[col] = pd.Categorical(df[col],
categories=df[col].unique()).codes
df['predicted_rating']=rf.predict(df[features])
top_performers=df.groupby('contractor_id')['predicted_rating'].mean().sort_values(ascending=False)[:3]
```

#### IV. RESULTS

##### A. Algorithm's Output

The output of the algorithm is the list of contractors who is the top performers among the list of contractors enrolled for work. The minimum requirement for do an analysis is the commitment of at least one work per contractor.

Admin of labour management system can have option to send a greeting / certificate of appreciation to the top of the contractors after the analysis. The PDF version of the

certificates will be available for the concerned contractors to view and download

##### B. Findings

- The top performers always based on their punctuality, timeliness, affordability,
- Higher the value of the above features, higher the rank of contractor

##### C. Accuracy

The scores of accuracy and precision were also estimated within the code itself. The determined values shows a great level of performance that can be deployed in production environment.

The accuracy obtained for this model is 0.89 and the precision of the model is 0.81

After the evaluation of model using Mean-squared error, Root Mean squared Error and R-Squared error, it shows a reasonable value.

```
MSE: 0.0008000000000000014
RMSE: 0.028284271247461926
R-squared score: 0.9993263157894737
```

#### V. CONCLUSION

With the inclusion of this machine learning approach of predicting best performers among all the contractors enrolled in this system, human resource management like rewarding top performers could be enhanced. The way of managing contractors in this way is quite efficient and durable. Surely this will unwrap people who is sincerely working for the mission of organization, people who shows continuous delay and bad revenue etc.

#### VI. FUTURE SCOPE

The work presented in this paper is merely just one of the way organizations can depend to fetch relevant patterns for the identification of valuable employees ( in this context contractors). For proceeding with large industrial projects or commercial labor management, it is better consider more data collected during the progression of contracted works like tool sets used, number of times consultations conducted with customer, count of pitfalls and loss in profit etc. But this data can't be selected easily as the above method. As organization grows up, based on their demand and human resources , it

will become a requirement for the effective analysis of contractors and other important roles.

With the application of deep learning and the incorporation of intensive sentimental analysis using advanced natural language processing techniques can enhance the way of HR analytics in a strong and reliable way.

## VII. REFERENCES

- [1] Patel ,“Ranker: An AI -Based Employee Performance Classification scheme to Rank and Identify Low Performers”- October 2022
- [2] Huang, X., Zhang, Y., & Zhou, Z. (2017). A random forest approach for predicting contractor performance in construction projects. *Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems*, 32(5), 3365-3373.
- [3] Zhang, X., Wang, Y., & Hu, Y. (2020). Prediction of contractor performance in construction projects based on random forest and fuzzy comprehensive evaluation. *Advances in Civil Engineering*, 2020, 1-13.
- [4] Chen, W., & Zhang, Y. (2020). Contractor performance prediction in construction projects using a novel random forest model. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2020, 1-12.
- [5] Ding, L., & Wang, Z. (2018). Contractor performance prediction in construction projects using a random forest model with principal component analysis. *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, 32(2), 04017065.
- [6] Li, Y., Zhao, X., & Zeng, H. (2021). A comparative study of machine learning methods for contractor performance prediction in construction projects. *Automation in Construction*, 125, 103621.
- [7] Chen, Z., Wang, L., & Zhou, Y. (2020). Contractor performance prediction in construction projects using a random forest model with feature selection. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, 38(4), 4721-4729.
- [8] Wang, C., Cheng, J., & Wang, W. (2019). Prediction of contractor performance in construction projects using a hybrid approach combining random forest and support vector regression. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, 36(5), 4475-4483.